

TECHNICAL REPORT

D7.2: Dissemination and Communication Plan update 1

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DELIVERABLE FACTSHEET

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Abstract	The Dissemination and Communications Plan provides the ANGIE project with a solid framework, roadmap, and practical tools to help disseminate project results and activities. This report provides the details of the efforts taken and the results at the halfway point of the ANGIE project. The report describes the efforts undertaken to publicize the goals and results of the ANGIE project to target audiences so far: specifically, this involves the setting up of the ANGIE website, social media accounts, workshops and conferences that have been organized, scientific publications, and conference presentations.
Keywords	Dissemination; communication;

HISTORY OF CHANGES

Version	Date	Creation / Change	Page
1.0	12/01/2022	Document approved by all Partners	All

PROJECT CONSORTIUM

Participant No.	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
1. (Coordinator)	Swiss Federal Institute of Technology Zürich	ETH	Switzerland
2.	University of Würzburg	UoW	Germany
3.	University of Barcelona	UoB	Spain
4.	University of Crete	UoC	Greece
5.	Stroke Alliance for Europe (SAFE)	SAFE	Pan-European
6.	Experian	EXP	Portugal
7.	Magnebotix	MGBX	Switzerland
8.	Discovery Foundation	DF	Greece
9.	Verhaert	VERT	Belgium

1. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable is part of the Work Package 7 (WP7) and is the first update of the ANGIE Communication and Dissemination plan that was submitted in M6 (June 2021). This deliverable outlines the implemented dissemination activities for the first period (M24) of the project. Beyond listing the implemented activities, it also describes the evolutionary process of the ANGIE dissemination approach and highlights the expected interactions with the ANGIE community and beyond.

1.1. Scope

The present document is the Deliverable 7.2 "D7.2: Dissemination and Communication Plan update 1" (henceforth referred to as D7.2). The main objectives of D7.2 are to provide an updated version of the Communication and Dissemination plan and to report the dissemination and communication activities performed during the first period (M24) of the project. The ANGIE Dissemination and Communication Plan has been created with the aim of setting up a framework developed by the consortium to help with projects communications in creating awareness, disseminating results and engaging stakeholders. A range of dissemination and communication activities have been implemented to deliver appropriate content to:

- local and regional authorities in the EU;
- research community and experts from diverse fields;
- entrepreneurs and industry;
- the general public and other stakeholders;

1.2. Audience

This document (D7.2) is available to the public and the European Commission.

2. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION TOOLS

The Consortium partners have been actively implementing the Dissemination and Communication Plan and held 14 meetings in the period February 10, 2021- October 12, 2022, to discuss, organize, coordinate, and plan dissemination and communication activities. In this section of the report each of our identified channels is covered in detail in respect to the communication and dissemination activities which have taken place.

2.1. ANGIE logo

The creation of the logo is of a great importance since it establishes the project's visual identity and supports our recognition. The ANGIE logo is used in every promotional material and channel as well as outcome of the project (reports, website, social media, newsletters, etc.). The final ANGIE logo is illustrated in the following figure.

2.2. ANGIE website

The ANGIE website¹ serves as a central hub for the project's identity, news and updates. It includes all the project information, such as project objectives, methodology, expected contribution, consortium members, dissemination material and social media. The website contains information on the ANGIE Innovation Ecosystem, the events organised by the project and includes all the project results freely downloadable. The website is continuously updated throughout the project duration, is monitored via Google Analytics, is GDPR-compliant and all visitors can read the privacy policy.

2.3. Social media accounts

To ensure communication and dissemination activities, Social Media accounts have been created on LinkedIn², Twitter³ and YouTube⁴ channel. The accounts of ANGIE in social media are the following:

LinkedIn: [ANGIE_h2020](https://www.linkedin.com/company/angie-h2020)

Twitter: [@angie_h2020](https://twitter.com/angie_h2020)

¹ <https://h2020-angie.eu>

² <https://www.linkedin.com/company/angie-h2020>

³ https://twitter.com/angie_h2020

⁴ https://www.youtube.com/@angie_h2020

YouTube: ANGIE Project

During the first period, posts have been continuously published on the ANGIE Social Media accounts. Our content is constantly monitored and evaluated in order to ascertain what is most appealing and attractive to our audience. Our website provides direct access to these social networks by clicking on the icons situated on the footer part of the website. In addition, dissemination through the partners' social media accounts is implemented by sharing information and news about the project to increase stakeholders' participation. Constant communication and regular promotion of news to the various communities through such media will be continuously pursued until the end of the project life to increase the ANGIE impact. Figures and analytics of our social media accounts are provided in ANNEX1⁵.

2.4. ANGIE Newsletter

The ANGIE newsletter ensures both communication and dissemination at different levels (EU and US) and keeps the stakeholders up to date with the findings of the project, inform about other relevant events, publications and key policy developments.

ANGIE Newsletter, Issue 1, November 2022⁶

The first issue of the ANGIE Newsletter was launched in November 2022 and included general information on the ANGIE project, information on events that ANGIE consortium organised and events in which ANGIE representatives participated. The Newsletter has been disseminated to our social media accounts, the Zenodo ANGIE Community and is available on the website as well. In addition, using the information of the first report D6.1, where we identified researchers, start-ups, entrepreneurship organizations, policy makers, journalists and news outlets we created an email list⁷ and we shared our newsletter to communicate the project's scope and deliver our latest news, actions and results.

2.5. ANGIE Chat Lab

In November 2022, Chat Lab was initiated on the webpage of ANGIE project (<https://h2020-angie.eu/chat-lab/>). Chat Lab is a platform for everyone. Through this platform we aim to initiate conversations between experts on issues related to Targeted Drug Delivery and people from the public or other experts, entrepreneurs, researchers, startups, etc. Participants of the Working Groups as well as members of the Consortium can interact with anyone that is interested either on the project itself or about Targeted Drug Delivery topics. The user of the platform can choose any of the profiles that are available on the Chat Lab page according to the expertise of each Working Group member. Then on, an easy way to contact the expert has been inserted. An overview of the chat lab platform and the individual expert profiles can be seen below:

⁵ ANNEX 1

⁶ ANNEX 2

⁷ ANNEX 3

Chat Lab: meet the experts

Chat Lab is a place for everyone!

Here you will find experts from the ANGIE project as well as researchers and experts from all over the world, ready to answer all of your questions.

Click on the profile of the expert / researcher you would like to contact.

ANGIE the future of drug delivery

Home | Project | Kick-start | Team | **Chat Lab** | Events | News | Contact

Andreea-Iulia Someșan
Talk to me about ethics and patient acceptance of drug delivery methods.

Maria J. Blanco-Prieto
Talk to me about advanced drug delivery systems to treat cancer, cardiovascular and neurodegenerative disease.

Dr Romina Fucà
Talk to me about how to manage fear of introduction of new targeted drug delivery technologies can affect individuals.

2.6. ANGIE Meetup Group

We created the Nanotechnology for Targeted Drug Delivery Meetup Group (<https://www.meetup.com/nanotechnology-for-targeted-drug-delivery-meetup-group/>) which is now part of Nanotechnology for Targeted Drug Delivery Meetup Network. Through this platform we connected with technology and entrepreneurship meetup groups in EU, with people who are working in related fields to our own, that offer a variety of networking opportunities, and attended online networking, educational and entrepreneurship events.

Organizer

ANGIE
the future of drug delivery
Nanotechnology for Targeted Drug Delivery Meetup Group

Member

Impact Hub Lisbon - Events & Meetups
Munich Startup Founder 101
Health Technology Forum: Berlin
STEM 4 Health Warsaw
Meetup E-Santé & Health Tech
Health Hack Academy Stockholm

Part of **Nanotechnology for Targeted Drug Delivery Meetup Network**

Nanotechnology for Targeted Drug Delivery Meetup Group

Brussels, Belgium

12 members · Public group

Organized by **Discovery Foundation**

2.6. ANGIE Zenodo Community

We created the ANGIE Zenodo Community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/angie-h2020eu/>). Built and developed by researchers, Zenodo is an online repository for EU-funded research that promotes Open Data and Science with more of 10,000 communities for researchers, medicals and public persons. The

ANGIE Zenodo Community gathers all public deliverables, scientific publications and publicly available results of the project under one place. All the documents included in the Zenodo Community are under open access status and are freely available. All dissemination material produced for the project are already available, including newsletters. The ANGIE Zenodo Community is being continuously updated with new publicly available content on targeted drug delivery and research results on microrobots targeting the brain.

ANGIE - MAGnetically steerable wireless Nanodevices for the tarGeted delivery of therapeutic agents in any vascular rEgion of the body

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February 8, 2022 (1) [Journal article](#) [Open Access](#) [View](#)

Magnetically Assisted Robotic Fetal Surgery for the Treatment of Spina Bifida
 Simone Gevasori, Jonas Lussi, Silvia Viviani, Quentin Boehler, Nicole Ochsenbein, Ueli Moehrlen, Bradley J. Nelson,
 Spina bifida is a congenital defect that occurs on the vertebral spine of a fetus. The most severe form causes exposure of the spinal cord and spinal nerve and has important repercussions on the life of the newborn child. Current prenatal operative procedures require laparotomy of the abdomen as well
 Uploaded on December 22, 2022
 Published in IEEE Transactions on Medical Robotics and Bionics

October 7, 2021 (1) [Journal article](#) [Open Access](#) [View](#)

Powering and Fabrication of Small-Scale Robotics Systems
 Salvador Pané, Pedro Wendel-García, Yonca Belce, Xiang-Zhong Chen, Josep Puigmartí-Luis
 Purpose of Review: The increasing number of contributions in the field of small-scale robotics is significantly associated with the progress in material science and process engineering during the last half century. With the objective of integrating the most optimal materials for the propulsion of these
 Uploaded on December 22, 2022
 Published in NANOROBOTICS AND MICROROBOTICS

Mar 26, 2022 (1) [Journal article](#) [Open Access](#) [View](#)

Toward More Inclusive Networks and Initiatives in Innovation Ecosystems: Protocol for a Systematic Review
 Georgia Itina, Eirini Mavromanolaki, Andreas D Flouris
 Expanding the cooperation and enlarging the participation of more diverse stakeholders within innovation ecosystems will increase their efficiency and capacity to contribute at local, regional, and national levels. This paper presents the protocol for a systematic review that will identify &id
 Uploaded on December 22, 2022
 Published in JMIR Research Protocols

September 27, 2021 (1) [Conference paper](#) [Open Access](#) [View](#)

Magnetic small-scale robots: Principles, applications and challenges
 S. Pané, J. Puigmartí, M. Pinto, E. Mavromanolaki, A. D. Flouris, T. S. Mayor, T. C. Lühmann, D. Sargent, B. J. Nelson
 Last two decades has seen a growth of the research on untethered mobile small-scale robots. These motile devices display the ability to travel through fluids by transforming the energy generated by an external power source into mechanical motion. As a result, these devices are being recognized as pr
 Uploaded on December 22, 2022

Community

angie
 the future of drug delivery

ANGIE - MAGnetically steerable wireless Nanodevices for the tarGeted delivery of therapeutic agents in any vascular rEgion of the body

This repository community collects research outputs related to the ANGIE project. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 952152.

MAGnetically steerable wireless Nanodevices for the tarGeted delivery of therapeutic agents in any vascular rEgion of the body – ANGIE - aims to develop a novel, minimally invasive approach for treatment of strokes.

Most strokes occur when a blood vessel in the brain is occluded by a clot. This clot then prevents areas in the brain from being supplied with oxygen, resulting in the sudden death of brain tissue. Strokes are a leading cause of death and disability worldwide, and stroke cases are expected to rise in the coming years. The most common treatment for this kind of stroke involves injecting a thrombolytic drug (usually tPA) into the blood, which then dissolves the clot. Tiny mobile magnetic devices are showing huge potential for future biomedical applications. The EU-funded ANGIE project will forge ahead with small-scale robotics, magnetic navigation systems and localized targeted drug delivery. Specifically, the project will develop magnetically steerable wireless nanodevices for the targeted delivery of therapeutic agents via the body's vascular system. By creating a baseline of knowledge and skills for localized targeted drug delivery, the project will increase health professionals' capacity to treat multiple chronic diseases. Moreover, it will enable doctors to deliver drugs precisely where needed with minimal side effects.

2.7. ANGIE podcast

The "ANGIE podcast" is our consortium's way to Discuss topics around targeted drug delivery (TDD), to increase visibility and awareness about the use of nanotechnology in TDD applications, answer emerging questions from the public, discuss unpopular opinions with the help of experts of different fields and create a community with the most updated information on issues around TDD.

angie
 Home | The Project | Kick-start programme | Team | Chat Lab | Events | News | Contact

Home / Podcast

The "ANGIE podcast" is our consortium's way to

- Discuss topics around targeted drug delivery (TDD),
- Increase visibility and awareness about the use of nanotechnology in TDD applications,
 - Answer emerging questions from the public,
 - Discuss unpopular opinions with the help of experts of different fields and
- Create a community with the most updated information on issues around TDD.

Stay tuned! Our new episodes are coming!

Episode 1 [View](#)

Episode 2 [View](#)

Episode 3 [View](#)

Episode 4 [View](#)

Episode 5 [View](#)

3. DISSEMINATING OUR RESULTS TO LOCAL/REGIONAL AUTHORITIES IN THE EU

We disseminated our vision, project goals, and preliminary results in reports, articles in specialized press, newsletters, and press releases suited to reach individuals in local/regional authorities. The Dissemination and Communication Plan stipulates that Partners accompany all our scientific publications with policy briefs and press releases to maximize the potential for reaching this audience.

3.1. European Stroke Awareness Day

We launched ANGIE on European Stroke Awareness Day on 11 May 2021. A press release was issued, alongside content for digital channels which included videos of the principal investigators and visual assets for social media. Stroke Alliance for Europe shared across their own digital channels (<https://www.safestroke.eu/2021/05/10/launch-of-new-eu-stroke-research-project/>) and with their members (stroke support organisations): press release, presentation slides; information factsheet and social media assets. Twenty stroke support organisations in Europe translated and disseminated to their stakeholders with an estimated minimum reach: 200,000

Launch of new EU stroke research project.

May 10, 2021

New research announced today (11 May 2021), European Stroke Awareness Day will develop micro-robots to unblock blood vessels and fight stroke from within.

A new ground-breaking project, ANGIE, funded by the EU, aims to develop nano-surgeons that will enter the body to treat blood clots.

The ANGIE project will develop a radical, new technology for localised, targeted drug delivery based on steerable wireless nanodevices, capable of navigating the body vascular system to deliver drugs where no other instrument can go. ANGIE will offer health professionals vastly improved intervention capacity to tackle multiple chronic diseases and enable them to deliver drugs precisely where needed, with minimal side effects.

Read more www.h2020-angie.eu and <https://www.safestroke.eu/angie/>

3.2. Brain Awareness Week

ANGIE was promoted during Brain Awareness Week, on March 14, 2022. The awareness week is a global campaign that aims to foster public enthusiasm and support for brain science. We created a news article and social media posts to promote the research, linking back to the principal investigator video and the ANGIE website ANGIE – targeted treatment using microbots . Seventeen stroke support organisations in Europe translated and disseminated this to their stakeholders with an estimated reach of 200,000.

Brain Awareness Week 2022

A A A

This awareness week is a global campaign to engage the general public in brain science, and the impact brain research has on our everyday lives.

We are supporting Brain Awareness Week this year by sharing the latest news and development in the six EU research project grants we are involved in.

We want to raise awareness of stroke research in Europe and encourage involvement and participation in EU research.

Find out more about the latest developments:

ANGIE

The ANGIE project is developing a novel approach for the treatment of strokes, by magnetically steering microrobots to the site of the brain bleed. Read more about this exciting new technology [here](#)

4. DISSEMINATING OUR RESULTS TO THE RESEARCH COMMUNITY AND EXPERTS FROM DIVERSE FIELDS

ANGIE has already published three (3) scientific publications in high impact scientific journals (peer reviewed). In addition, ANGIE partners have organised/participated in conference sessions, workshops and events. Several scientific papers and patents are currently in preparation or under review.

4.1. Scientific Publications

Open access is provided to all scientific publications in gold format.

- Salvador Pané, Pedro Wendel-Garcia, Yonca Belce, Xiang-Zhong Chen & Josep Puigmartí-Luis. Powering and Fabrication of Small-Scale Robotics Systems. *Curr Robot Rep* 2, 427– 440 (2021).
- Ntina G., Mavromanolaki E, Flouris AD. Toward More Inclusive Networks and Initiatives in Innovation Ecosystems: Protocol for a Systematic Review. *JMIR Res Protoc*. 2022;11(5):e34071
- Simone Gervasoni; Jonas Lussi; Silvia Viviani; Quentin Boehler; Nicole Ochsenbein; Ueli Moehrlen; Bradley J. Nelson. Magnetically Assisted Robotic Fetal Surgery for the Treatment of Spina. *IEEE Transactions on Medical Robotics and Bionics*, 4(1), pp. 85-93, Feb. 2022.

4.2. Conferences

ANGIE has organised/participated in scientific conferences and its outcomes have been presented to the Research community. The following list includes the ANGIE publications that have been presented in Conferences. Open access is provided to all scientific publications in gold/green format. Pictures taken during conferences and events can be found in ANNEX 4.

ANGIE Satellite Symposium 2021

ANGIE partners organized a satellite symposium during the 2021 Bionanotox conference to showcase our work up to that point as well as our plans for the future. The main topic of Bionanotox Conference is Bio Nano-toxicology that lies on the interface of several scientific fields, such as biology, chemistry, toxicology, computational science chemistry, nanotechnology and biotechnology. The

Conference is a continuation of a long-term co-operation between scientists of these fields, which has been ongoing for the last 20 years, in the frame of the bilateral scientific state programs. Scientists working in the most prominent Universities, Technological Institutes and Companies as well as distinguished field specialists coming from several countries attended this Conference. The proceedings from this symposium have been included in a journal supplement published in Public Health Toxicology.

- Herrera-Restrepo, R. S., P. Martinez-Bulit, A. D. Flouris, M. Pinto, R. Moreira, E. Mavromanolaki, T. S. Mayor, S. Pané, J. Ignés, and J. Puigmartí-Luis. In flow controlled synthesis of blood clots." Public Health Toxicology 1, no. Supplement (2021).
- Mavromanolaki, E., Ntina, G., Karatsali, S., Smarianaki, P., Pinto, M., Moreira, R., Pané, S., Mayor, T.S., Puigmartí, J. and Flouris, A.D., 2021. Evolution, gaps, and trends in the origins of innovation ecosystems. Public Health Toxicology, no. Supplement (2021).
- Meiners, K., Richter, M., Landers, F., Pané, S. and Lühmann, T., 2021. Marrying inorganics and biologics: Opportunities and challenges. Public Health Toxicology 1, no. Supplement (2021).
- Pané, S., J. Puigmartí, M. Pinto, E. Mavromanolaki, A. D. Flouris, T. S. Mayor, T. C. Lühmann, D. Sargent, and B. J. Nelson. Magnetic small-scale robots: Principles, applications and challenges. Public Health Toxicology 1, no. Supplement (2021).
- Puigmartí-Luis, J., 2021. Microfluidic technologies for chemistry, materials science and biotechnology. Public Health Toxicology 1, no. Supplement (2021).
- Landers, F., C. J. Alcantara, J. Puigmartí-Luis, B. J. Nelson, and S. Pané. Soft-hard magnetically driven microrobotic devices." Public Health Toxicology 1, no. Supplement (2021).

The Hamlyn Symposium on Medical Robotics 2022

Derick Sivakumaran (MGBX) presented a paper on “In Vitro Navigation of a Magnetic Sphere using a Model Predictive Controller for Neurovascular Targeted Drug Delivery Applications”.

International Conference on Manipulation, Automation, and Robotics at Small Scales (MARSS)

Fabian Landers (ETHZ) participated in MARSS, the International Conference on Manipulation, Automation, and Robotics at Small Scales, held in Toronto, Canada. During a Special session on Micro/Nanorobots for drug and/or cell delivery, he presented the paper “3D interlocked metal-organic magnetic microrobots”.

Barts Research and Advanced Interventional Neuroradiology (BRAIN)

ANGIE partners participated in the Barts Research and Advanced Interventional Neuroradiology (BRAIN) Conference in London. Fabian Landers gave a presentation entitled “Medical Micro & Nanorobots: From the Lab to the Hospital” and reports: “It was great and insightful to listen to some of the leading Doctors and Researchers in the field and discuss our technology with them. Getting feedback from medical professionals is crucial to ensure a smooth translation of the ANGIE technology into hospitals.”

5. HOSTING AND ATTENDING INDUSTRY/NETWORK EVENTS

5.1. The Japanese-European Workshop on Moonshot program

The ANGIE consortium was invited to attend the Japanese-European Workshop on Moonshot program goal 3 “Co-evolving AI and Robots towards 2050” which took place in Switzerland from September 21 to 23, 2022. A delegation from Japan consisting of 25 researchers attended the event in order to seek potential collaboration partners from Europe. The delegation was accompanied by representatives from the Japan Science and Technology Agency JST and the Science & Technology Office Tokyo (STO), Embassy of Switzerland in Japan. The Moonshot Research and Development Program promotes high-risk, high-

impact R&D based on ambitious and inspiring ideas to achieve disruptive innovation and radical solutions for social issues by 2050.

5.2. Emerging Issues on Targeted Drug Delivery

The primary aim of this event was to get feedback from individuals out of the Consortium or the Working Groups on the issues they foresee arising by the eventual use of nanomedicine in Targeted Drug Delivery. Secondary aims were to brainstorm on the existing topics that have been suggested to be discussed in the proposed book and suggest future activities for the Working Groups. The online event was organised for the 28th November 2022 (16:00 CET) and took place on Zoom. The meeting was constituted by 2 sections. One section was the introductory presentation and presentations from experts on Targeted Drug Delivery from different scientific fields and the second was a “Question and Answer” session where everyone had the chance to ask questions to the speakers. The speakers were all members of the Consortium as well as member of the Working groups that were created.

5.3. Targeted drug delivery for cardiovascular and cerebrovascular diseases meetup event

In December 2022, we organized the Meetup event “Targeted Drug delivery for Cardiovascular and Cerebrovascular Diseases”. This online ANGIE Meetup event brought together medical experts in cardiovascular and cerebrovascular diseases with the ambition to generate new research collaborations and future applications. The meetup event provided medical doctors, engineers, scientists, new researchers and stakeholders from different disciplines with a unique and exciting format to learn the most current information about nano-carriers in the diagnosis and treatment of cardiovascular and cerebrovascular diseases. The event was the perfect platform to share, experience, foster collaborations across health care, pharmaceutical, biotech & diagnostic industries with hospitals and academia.

6. ORGANIZING TECHNICAL WORKSHOPS ON IMPLEMENTATION AND OPERATION OF ANGIE AND IDEA COMPETITIONS

We developed a concept with two subsequent open innovation programmes to strengthen links between universities, industry and the start-up community, leading to greater research translation and commercialisation.

The ANGIE Kickstart programme, running from October 2022 until May 2023, invited students, researchers, clinicians, and other healthcare professionals (medical devices industry, pharmaceutical companies, etc.) to define a project/venture for developing an application” on the ANGIE “platform. In combination with a series of workshops, mentoring, and support from the centers of entrepreneurship of the consortium partners, this program effectively creates a network of individuals who share similar perspectives and values with respect to targeted drug delivery. After the completion of the program, promising projects will be selected in an open competition to participate in the subsequent program.

The ANGIE Acceleration programme, will run from the fall of 2023 to the spring of 2024, will support teams, that have successfully completed the kick-start program, and will be selected to continue to validate the business viability and technological feasibility of the concept. During the course of the programme, workshops will be conducted on topics related to technical, business, and financial aspects. Moreover, participating teams will have access to R&D facilities and subject matter experts as well as dedicated mentoring.

6.1. ANGIE KICKSTART PROGRAMME

The ANGIE Kick-start Programme, an initiative from the ANGIE project, is open for students, researchers, and healthcare professionals with an interest for targeted drug delivery. It starts with an idea for a targeted drug delivery intervention for treatment of a certain health condition and finishes with a definition of the concept, a viable business case and a prototype development plan.

The programme provides participants with mentored experiences in healthcare innovation through a combination of workshop activities, focused project work, and other appropriate professional development and networking opportunities. The programme draws on the many facets of the activities established in the ANGIE project, as well as the network of our academia and industry partners and external stakeholders.

The programme and its various activities is running from October 2022 until May 2023. During this period, participants work on their concepts under the supervision of their mentors. Expert-mentors from the participating organizations meet with the teams to provide guidance and feedback once a month.

Kick-start participants will benefit from a collaborative, open innovation process and access to a community of like-minded researchers, entrepreneurs and innovators.

We embedded a web-page in our website (www.h2020-angie.eu/innovation-ecosystem) where candidates could find all the relevant information about the Programme and the registration form as well.

The Angie Kick-start was promoted through our website, Twitter and LinkedIn account. In addition, all partners contributed for the promotion of the Programme and shared the ANGIE kick-start brochure through their network, websites and social media.

In October 2022, we held an online informative webinar session on the ANGIE kick-start Programme. Participants learned about the ANGIE project and its approach to targeted drug delivery. Moreover, we explained what the kick-start programme is and how we can support them to get started with the ANGIE technology platform.

Agenda

Thank you for joining us today!

- Welcome and introductions
- Overview of the ANGIE Kick-start Programme, **Gina Ntina**, Discovery Foundation
- The state of the technology and its applications, **Fabian Landers**, ETH Zürich
- The importance of stroke research in saving lives and reducing disability after stroke, **Arlene Wilkie**, SAFE
- Practical information of the ANGIE kick-start Programme, **Benoit De Vrieze**, VERHAERT Masters in Innovation
- **Meet the other participants**, Take the opportunity to introduce yourself and share your interest in targeted drug delivery therapies.
- Q&A
- Wrap up

ANGIE kick-start programme

30.10.2022 3

Frequently asked questions

Can I work on any idea?

You can participate with any targeted drug delivery idea based on your interest and expertise.

Working alone or in a team?

We advise to work in a team of 2-3 people with different backgrounds

What will happen to the results of our work?

Your idea and project remain yours. We only require you to pitch it at the final bootcamp.

ANGIE Innovation Ecosystem

- The ANGIE innovation ecosystem brings together health professionals, researchers, entrepreneurs and manufacturers providing them with online courses and technical workshops to understand the innovation aspects of the new technology and giving them examples of applications in different fields.

- We create new market opportunities for entrepreneurs, companies and investors.

ANGIE kick-start programme

30.10.2022

Project Overview – The Concept of ANGIE

Small-Scale Robots and Magnetic Navigation Systems

Helical Magnetic Microbot for in vitro drug delivery

Magnetic Navigation System for cardiac ablation with magnetic steerable catheters

Currently, the ANGIE kick-start Programme candidates have been assigned to their teams and participated to the first workshop “Discovering the clinical journey” where we helped them understand the current clinical journey for the health condition or disease they have chosen to focus on. This workshop provided them with the entire sequence of events that a patient experiences within a given healthcare system or across providers, from scheduling an appointment for a regular check-up to receiving treatment for a certain disease. Participants designed a personalized patient journey map of the medical condition they are focusing on, which was a useful strategy to employ during the development of their targeted drug delivery treatment.

In addition, they have been provided with personalized mentoring sessions on technical and innovation aspects. Expert-mentors within our consortium guide them through the development of their projects, connect them with a broader network and increase their entrepreneurship engagement.

7. PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

ANGIE consortium has set specific targets in order to maximize the impact of the project. The “Dissemination targets” table was submitted as D7.1 in M6. These targets are shown in the following table as well, which is used to keep track of the targets’ achievement so far. This report provides a guideline for all communication and dissemination activities carried out in the project, indicating that the ANGIE consortium has been following successfully the initial Dissemination and Communication Plan. The dissemination activities conducted by ANGIE, enabled future advancements in this field of targeted drug delivery, as well as opportunities to enhance future cooperative efforts.

Indicator	Target	as of M24	Status
Scientific papers published	>15	3	on track
External events & conferences	>20	7	on track
Visits to ANGIE web-portal	>20,000	7,500	on track
Followers on social media	>5.000	120/5,500	(SAFE/ANGIE) has 3500 on Twitter, 2000 on Facebook
Views of promotional videos	>5000	0	Video to be released in March 2023
Newsletter/subscribers	10 / >1000	One / TBD	1st ANGIE newsletter just released. eNewsletter from SAFE includes ANGIE news and has 3200 subscribers
Synergies with other initiatives	>15	TBD	Work in progress
Exposure to policy events	>10	0	Scheduled for March 2023
Total stakeholders reached	>30,000	~220,000	ANGIE outreach through SAFE is estimated to be ~ 200,000. LinkedIn > 20,000 In-person > 160
Interdisciplinary working groups (T1.1)	4 / >2x per year	4	Interdisciplinary working groups were formed. Notably, the working groups started to meet to discuss ideas and find novel approaches.
Public debates (T1.2)	4 / >100 people	TBD	Scheduled for March 2023
Centres for Entrepreneurs (T6.2)	>5	1	ANGIE Kick-start has been launched
Local government meeting (T6.3)	>10	1	We participated in one local government meeting in Zurich on the future of healthcare.
Industry events (T6.4)	8 / >100 people	2 / 500	At B.R.A.I.N. 2022 and ANGIE Meetup event with experts in Cardiovascular and Cerebrovascular Diseases, results were disseminated and discussed with medical professionals and members of the medical device industry.
Technical online courses (T6.5)	>4 / 5000 views	1	Due to IP-filing, the online courses were not released to the public yet.

Technical workshops (T6.6)	>4 / 50 people	2 / 40	Technical and scientific (online-) Workshops were held between M1 and M24
Idea competitions (T6.7)	4 / 50 people	2/ 30	Idea-competitions were kicked off from the working groups and further evolved.

ANNEX 1

ANNEX 2

NEWSLETTER
ISSUE 1
NOVEMBER 2022

Newsletter
Issue 1
November 2022

Newsletter
Issue 1
November 2022

In ANGIE, we develop microbots for targeted drug delivery treatment of conditions such as strokes.

Magnetically steerable wireless Nanodevices for the targeted delivery of therapeutic agents in any vascular rEgion of the body

Magnetically steerable wireless Nanodevices for the targeted delivery of therapeutic agents in any vascular rEgion of the body – ANGIE is an innovative EU-funded research project which aims to develop a novel, minimally invasive approach for treatment of strokes.

What does the ANGIE project do?

Most strokes occur when a blood vessel in the brain is occluded by a clot. This clot then prevents areas in the brain from being supplied with oxygen, resulting in the sudden death of brain tissue. Strokes are a leading cause of death and disability worldwide, and stroke cases are expected to rise in the coming years. The most common treatment for this kind of stroke involves injecting a thrombolytic drug (usually rtPA) into the blood, which then dissolves the clot.

We hope you enjoy reading our first newsletter!

Dear Reader,
Welcome to the ANGIE project's first newsletter!

The four-year project started in January 2020 and involves partners from across Europe.

Team Members

Prof. Salvador Pané Vidal
Project Coordinator

In this issue, we introduce you to the ANGIE project. The central aim of the project is to a novel approach for treating strokes. By magnetically steering microbots to the clot, we can deliver rtPA directly to the stroke site. This approach allows us to deliver higher concentrations of rtPA directly to the clot, while reducing the overall amount of rtPA used by a factor of 10,000.

Don't let their mini size fool you! Tiny mobile magnetic devices are showing huge potential for future biomedical applications. The EU-funded ANGIE project will forge ahead with small-scale robotics, magnetic navigation systems and localised targeted drug delivery. Specifically, the project will develop magnetically steerable wireless nanodevices for the targeted delivery of therapeutic agents via the body's vascular system. By creating a baseline of knowledge and skills for localised targeted drug delivery, the project will increase health professionals' capacity to treat multiple chronic diseases. Moreover, it will enable doctors to deliver drugs precisely where needed with minimal side effects.

<http://www.h2020-angie.eu>
www.linkedin.com/company/angie-h2020
[@angie_h2020](https://twitter.com/angie_h2020)

Programme: H2020-EU.1.2.2. – FET Proactive | Call for Proposal: H2020-EI-FETPROACT-2018 | Funding Scheme: RIA – Research and Innovation action | Grant number: 962332 – ANGIE

Recent academic publications

The papers are developed to help advance the current state of the art in the field of micro/nanobots, and put forward our radically new technology which implies major progress in small-scale robotics, magnetic navigation systems, and localised targeted drug delivery. Also, to engage with relevant communities, policy makers, European organizations and citizens, and stakeholders to help us create an innovation ecosystem.

The ANGIE members published the following scientific articles:

- Salvador Pané, Pedro Wendel-García, Yonca Belce, Xiang-Zhong Chen & Josep Puigmarí-Luis. Powering and Fabrication of Small-Scale Robotics Systems. *Curr Robot Rep* 2, 427–440 (2021).
- Ntina G. Mavromanolaki E. Flouris AD. Toward More Inclusive Networks and Initiatives in Innovation Ecosystems: Protocol for a Systematic Review. *JMIR Res Protoc*. 2022;11(5):e34071.
- Simone Gervasoni, Jonas Lussi; Silvia Viviani; Quentin Boehler; Nicole Ochsenben; Ueli Moehrlen; Bradley J. Nelson. Magnetically Assisted Robotic Fetal Surgery for the Treatment of Spina Bifida. in *IEEE Transactions on Medical Robotics and Bionics*, 4(1), pp. 85-93, Feb. 2022.

Conferences and symposia

We have presented our finding in the following conferences, workshops, or symposia:

- Herrera-Restrepo, R. S., P. Martínez-Bullit, A. D. Flouris, M. Pinto, R. Moreira, E. Mavromanolaki, T. S. Mayor, S. Pané, J. Igñés, and J. Puigmarí-Luis. "In flow controlled synthesis of blood clots." *Public Health Toxicology* 1, no. Supplement (2021).
- Mavromanolaki, E., Ntina, G., Karatsali, S., Smarianiaki, P., Pinto, M., Moreira, R., Pané, S., Mayor, T.S., Puigmarí, J. and Flouris, A.D., 2021. Evolution, gaps, and trends in the origins of innovation ecosystems. *Public Health Toxicology*, 1(Supplement).
- Meiners, K., Richter, M., Landers, F., Pané, S. and Lühmann, T., 2021. Marrying inorganics and biologics: Opportunities and challenges. *Public Health Toxicology*, 1(Supplement).
- Pané, S., J. Puigmarí, M. Pinto, E. Mavromanolaki, A. D. Flouris, T. S. Mayor, T. C. Lühmann, D. Sargent, and B. J. Nelson. "Magnetic small-scale robots: Principles, applications and challenges." *Public Health Toxicology* 1, no. Supplement (2021).
- Puigmarí-Luis, J., 2021. Microfluidic technologies for chemistry, materials science and biotechnology. *Public Health Toxicology*, 1(Supplement).
- Landers, F., C. J. Alcantara, J. Puigmarí-Luis, B. J. Nelson, and S. Pané. "Soft-hard magnetically driven microbotic devices." *Public Health Toxicology* 1, no. Supplement (2021).
- D. Sivakumaran, F. C. Landers, Q. Boehler, C. Chautems, S. Pané, and B. J. Nelson. "In Vitro Navigation of a Magnetic Sphere using a Model Predictive Controller for Neurovascular Targeted Drug Delivery Applications." *The Hamlyn Symposium on Medical Robotics 2022*
- F. C. Landers and S. Pané. "3D Interlocked metal-organic magnetic microbots." *MARSS International conference on Manipulation, automation and robotics at small scales* (Toronto).

ANGIE Innovation Ecosystem

We create new market opportunities for entrepreneurs, companies and investors.

The ANGIE innovation ecosystem brings together health professionals, researchers, entrepreneurs and manufacturers providing them with online courses and antedtechual workshops to understand the innovation aspects of the new technology and giving them examples of applications in different fields.

ANGIE Kick-start Programme

Let's innovate together!

We want to inspire and enable ambitious students, inspiring researchers, experienced professionals and talented entrepreneurs to start addressing important medical challenges today while our technology is still under development.

Thus, we created the ANGIE kick-start to support participants to develop their own ideas for a targeted drug delivery intervention for treatment of a certain health condition. The programme consists of a series of workshops on targeted drug delivery and entrepreneurship topics. In addition, all participants will be mentored by an experienced venture builder, have access to leading experts in the field, and receive support to start a research project or a new venture.

In October 20, 2022 we held an info webinar on the ANGIE kick-start Programme. Participants learned about the ANGIE project and its approach to targeted drug delivery. Moreover, we explained what the kick-start programme is and how we can support them to get started with the technology platform.

The Hamlyn Symposium

In June 2022, ANGIE project researcher Derick Sivakumaran participated in the 14th Hamlyn Symposium on Medical Robotics and gave a presentation entitled "In Vitro Navigation of a Magnetic Sphere using a Model Predictive Controller for Neurovascular Targeted Drug Delivery Applications".

MARSS 2022

In July 2022, Fabian Landers participated in the International Conference on Manipulation, Automation and Robotics at Small Scales which was held in Toronto, Canada. During a Special session on Micro/Nano-robots for drug and/or cell delivery he presented our latest results on 3D Interlocked Micromachines

Recent events

12th International Bionanotex Conference

In October 2021, we organized a satellite symposium during the 2021 Bionanotex conference to showcase our work up to that point as well as our plans for the future. The proceedings from this symposium have been included in a journal supplement published in *Public Health Toxicology*.

ANGIE made six contributions to the annual BIONANOTEX conference in Crete. Unfortunately, due to the COVID-19 situation, the talks were held remotely.

Japanese-European Workshop on AI and Robotics

The Japanese-European Workshop on Moonshot program goal 3 "Co-evolving AI and Robots towards 2050" took place in Switzerland from September 21 to 23, 2022. A delegation from Japan consisting of 25 researchers attended the event in order to seek potential collaboration partners from Europe. We had some insightful talks and discussions about ongoing research and the 50 years ahead with some of the founders and current leaders of the field.

The delegation was accompanied by representatives from the Japan Science & Technology Agency JST and the Science & Technology Office Tokyo (STO), Embassy of Switzerland in Japan.

In November 2022, we held the online meeting Emerging Issues on Targeted Drug Delivery

The ANGIE project aims to change the way we practice medicine. In this light, pressing questions around issues related to communication, ethics, law, policy, and education should be discussed before the newly developed technology will be released. In our last event experts from around the world explored different issues around targeted drug delivery in clinical environments.

In December 2022, we participated the Barts Research and Advanced Interventional Neuro-radiology Conference. Fabian Landers gave a presentation entitled "Medical Micro & Nanobots: From the Lab to the Hospital" on 18/12/2022.

This ANGIE Meetup event pulled together medical experts in Cardiovascular and Cerebrovascular Diseases and focused on novel science, insights, tools and approaches for targeted drug delivery treatments.

Annex 3

ORGANIZATION	ORGANIZATION
KSA KANTONSSPITAL AARAU, SWITZERLAND	POPULATION HEALTH RESEARCH INSTITUTE, ONTARIO CANADA
CENTRE FOR RESEARCH IN MEDICAL DEVICES, NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND	NANOFLEX ROBOTICS
FUNDACIO ICTUS	CONSULTORIA E APLICAÇÕES EM SISTEMAS E TECNOLOGIA, LDA
DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICS, UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD	DEPARTMENT OF NEUROSCIENCES, KU LEUVEN
DEPARTMENT OF NEUROSCIENCES AND MENTAL HEALTH, HOSPITAL SANTA MARIA, UNIVERSITY OF LISBON	ORTHOROBOTICS
ESO	BIO INNOVATION INSTITUTE
SCHOOL OF MEDICINE, LILLE UNIVERSITY	IWA CONSULTING
CONSULTORIA E APLICAÇÕES EM SISTEMAS E TECNOLOGIA, LDA	WORLD STROKE ORGANISATION
CATALAN HEALTH SERVICE	WELLINGTON PARTNERS
BIOMEDPARTNERS	KULJETINPROTEIINI-VÄLITTEINEN LÄÄKEAINEIDEN KOHDENTAMINEN, TRANSPORTER GROUP
DEPARTMENT OF MECHANICAL ENGINEERING, IMPERIAL UK	TECHSTARS
TARGETED DRUG DELIVERY WITH NANOMEDICINE, UNIVERSITY OF GRONINGEN	TECHILL
TECHTOUR	INNOVATION FOR HEALTH 2023
PARIS REGION HEALTH CARE INNOVATION	ATHENS HACHING HEALTH
HELLENIC ALLICANCE FOR STROKE	STARTUPREPORTER
EU-STARTUPS	INSIGHT
EUROPEAN PROJECTS ASSOCIATION	ETN MAGAZINE
CARDIOLOGY UNIVERSITY, GENERAL HOSPITAL OF LARISSA, GREECE	LABORATORY OF NEUROGENETICS, DEPARTMENT OF NEUROLOGY, UNIVERSITY HOSPITAL OF LARISSA, GREECE
UNIVERSITY GENERAL, HOSPITAL OF HERAKLION, GREECE	BAWA BIOTECH LLC

EMPA, PARTICLES-BIOLOGY INTERACTIONS LAB	BIOPHARMACEUTICALS, UNIVERSITY OF GENEVA
BIOPHARMACEUTICALS SCIENCES, UNIVERSITY OF GENEVA	DEPARTMENT OF POLITICAL AND SOCIAL SCIENCES, UNIVERSITY OF FLORENCE
DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION SCIENCES, WEST UNIVERSITY OF TIMIȘOARA	PHARMACOECONOMICS AND OUTCOMES RESEARCH IBERIA
DEPARTMENT OF PHARMACY, PHARMACOLOGY AND HEALTH TECHNOLOGIES, UNIVERSITY OF LISBON	NUFFIELD COUNCIL ON BIOETHICS, KING'S COLLEGE LONDON
NATIONAL EHEALTH LIVING LAB, NETHERLANDS	CATALAN HEALTH SERVICE
DEPARTMENT OF ECONOMICS AND LAW, UNIVERSITY OF MACERATA	DEPARTMENT OF MEDICINE AND PSYCHOLOGY, SAPIENZA UNIVERSITY
EUROPEAN ALLIANCE OF ASSOCIATIONS FOR RHEUMATOLOGY	DEPARTMENT FOR HEALTH EVIDENCE, RADBOUD UNIVERSITY NIJMEGEN MEDICAL CENTRE
DEPARTMENT OF CLINICAL EPIDEMIOLOGY AND MEDICAL TECHNOLOGY ASSESSMENT (KEMTA), MAASTRICHT UNIVERSITY MEDICAL CENTRE	HEALTH TECHNOLOGY AND SERVICES RESEARCH DEPARTMENT, TECHNICAL MEDICAL CENTRE, UNIVERSITY OF TWENTE
NEUROLOGY DEPARTMENT, AZIENDA OSPEDALIERA SANT'ANNA HOSPITAL	DEPARTMENT OF HEALTH POLICY, LONDON SCHOOL OF ECONOMICS

ANNEX 4

Figure1: BRAIN Conference 2022

Figure 2: Japan-Europe Workshop on AI and Robots

Figure 3: International conference on Manipulation, automation and robotics at small scales, Toronto

Figure 4: The Hamlyn Symposium

the future of drug delivery

28 NOV
16:00 CET

Online meeting on “Emerging Issues on Targeted Drug Delivery”

Follow the link below to join via Zoom:
<https://us06web.zoom.us/j/85364799253?pwd=cmptTFd3ZXB4cUJhd0RkRFJWtG4vdz09>

Meeting Agenda

- Welcome and short presentation of the meeting
- Introduction, Impact of the ANGIE project, **Fabian Landers**
- Nanomedicine and drug delivery systems in cancer and regenerative medicine. **Prof. Maria Blanco-Prieto**
- Moral blindness in the context of clinical administration of drugs using wireless nanodevices technology, **Dr. Andreea-Iulia Someșan**
- Toxicity testing as a safety tool for Targeted Drug Delivery, **Dr. Polychronis Stivaltakakis**
- Society, policy and disruptive technology around targeted drug delivery, **Prof. Ernesto Gonzales**
- **Dr. Romina Fucà**
- Improved molecule to be used as a therapeutic solution to delay the progression of Parkinson’s disease, **Dr. Ana Clara Cristóvão**
- **Q&A session** after the presentations
- Summary of the meeting

*This is a public event. Anyone can join.

 Programme: H2020-EU.1.2.2 – FET Proactive | Call for Proposal: H2020-EI-FETPROACT-2019 | Funding Scheme: RIA – Research and Innovation action | Grant number 952152 – ANGIE

the future of drug delivery

28 NOV
16:00 CET

Online meeting on “Emerging Issues on Targeted Drug Delivery”

Professor Maria J. Blanco-Prieto

She is a full Professor of Pharmaceutical Technology at the University of Navarra. Her research on the drug delivery field is focused on the design, development and evaluation of advanced drug delivery systems.

She has significant experience in nanomedicine and tissue engineering with a focus on cancer, cardiovascular and neurodegenerative diseases.

Follow the link below to join via Zoom:
<https://us06web.zoom.us/j/85364799253?pwd=cmptTFd3ZXB4cUJhd0RkRFJWtG4vdz09>

 Programme: H2020-EU.1.2.2 – FET Proactive | Call for Proposal: H2020-EI-FETPROACT-2019 | Funding Scheme: RIA – Research and Innovation action | Grant number 952152 – ANGIE

the future of drug delivery

MAGnetically steerable wireless Nanodevices for the tarGeted delivery of therapeutic agents in any vascular rEgion of the body

FETPROACT-EIC-05-2019 – Project Number: 925152

ANGIE Emerging Issues on Targeted Drug Delivery

28.11.2022

Nanorobots in drug delivery: Sustainable supply chain issues

Ernesto DR Santibanez Gonzalez, PhD

Nov, 2022

Figure 8: Emerging Issues on Targeted Drug Delivery